

Immersed boundary method for high-order flux reconstruction based on volume penalization

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Abstract

In the last decade, there has been a lot of interest in developing high-order methods as viable option for unsteady scale-resolving-simulations which are increasingly important in the industrial design process. High-order methods offer the advantage of low numerical dissipation, high efficiency on modern architectures and quasi mesh-independence. Despite significant advances in high-order solution methods, the general CFD workflow (geometry, CAD preparation, meshing, solution, post-processing) has largely remained unchanged, with mesh generation being a significant bottleneck and often determining the overall quality of the solution. In this work, we aim to combine the numerical advantages of the high-order Flux Reconstruction (FR) method and the simplicity of the mesh generation (or lack thereof) of the Immersed Boundary Method (IBM) for steady and unsteady problems over moving geometries. The volume penalization (penalty-IBM) method is selected for its ease of implementation and robustness. Detailed discussions about numerical implementation, including the boundary representation, mask function, data reconstruction, and selection of the penalization parameter are given. Advantages of combining volume penalization in the high-order framework are shown by various numerical test cases. The approach is firstly demonstrated for the linear advection-diffusion equation by investigating the numerical convergence for the coupled FR-IBM approach. Thereafter, the accuracy of the approach is demonstrated for canonical (static) test cases in 2D and 3D when compared to a standard body-fitted unstructured simulation. Finally, the efficiency of the method to handle moving geometries is demonstrated for the flow around an airfoil with pitching and plunging motions.

Keywords: volume penalization, flux reconstruction, immersed boundary method, high-order method, moving boundary

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1. Introduction

24 Despite significant advantages, the general CFD workflow used in the industrial design process has largely
remained unchanged. The typical workflow consists of geometry definition, CAD preparation, meshing,
26 numerical solution, post-processing and subsequent design optimization. Of these, meshing is often the most
time consuming and can have a significant impact on the overall quality of solution. The bottleneck associated
28 with mesh generation could be eased with the development of mesh independent schemes or alternatively,
by developing methods designed for simple Cartesian grids via the Immersed Boundary Method (IBM). The
30 desire to achieve the former has been a motivating factor for the development of high-order schemes on
unstructured grids over the last decade. High-order methods are known to be more efficient for a given level
32 of accuracy, highly scalable on modern architectures [1, 2] and display a level of quasi mesh-independence
for industrially relevant problems [3, 4]. Examples of high-order methods include Discontinuous Galerkin
34 (DG) [5], Flux Reconstruction (FR) [6] and Spectral Difference (SD) [7] [8].

By contrast, the development of high-order methods on Cartesian grids for complex moving geometries
36 using IBM or related approaches has been relatively unexplored. One of the earliest proponents of exploring
this idea was Adrian Lew and his coworkers [9, 10] where the advantages and optimal order of convergence of
38 using the DG method over standard finite-differences for a 2D Poisson problem was reported. The method

was subsequently applied to problems in elasticity [11]. The solution of the Poisson problem with IBM and
40 DG was also considered in [12, 13] and in [14] for the Hybridized Discontinuous Galerkin (HDG) method.
The HDG method on irregular domains was also developed for the Navier-Stokes equations in [15]. Fidkowski
42 and Darmofal [16] were the first to report the use of cut-cell method to solve steady compressible flows over
two-dimensional geometries based on the DG and Finite Element Method (FEM). The high-order cut-cell
44 approach was also studied in [17, 18, 19] and more recently in [20] where stable discretizations on degenerate
meshes are presented for high-order finite-difference methods. While the cut-cell approaches are undoubtedly
46 superior on static grids, the extension to moving grids is far from straightforward.

The challenge to use high-order DG type methods for industrially relevant problems lies in the efficient
48 handling of complex geometries which can be combined with efficient Adaptive Mesh Refinement (AMR) and
highly optimized for Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) architectures [21, 22, 23]. Here, the IBM is a natural
50 choice and in this work we present an approach that combines the flexibility and ease of implementation
of the high-order FR method [6, 24, 25] on Cartesian grids with the IBM for moving geometries. The
52 approach utilizes the compact stencil of the high-order operators and offers the possibility of locally varying
the polynomial order for a more accurate representation of the boundary conditions than traditional finite
54 difference or finite volume methods. The flexibility of handling complex moving geometries stems from the
use of the IBM approach. Indeed, since its introduction [26], the IBM approach has been shown to be
56 versatile and applicable to a variety of problems ranging from flow over complex geometries [27], multiphase
flows [28] to Fluid Structure Interaction (FSI) [29, 30, 31]. In an IBM based approach the governing
58 equations (compressible or incompressible flow) are solved on a simple background Cartesian grid. The
methods can be differentiated by the way in which the influence of the immersed boundary on the fluid is
60 taken into account. This can be either through a cut-cell approach [32, 33, 34], ghost cell method [35, 36],
direct forcing [37, 38, 39] or by the introduction of penalization source terms [40] to take into account
62 the presence of the geometry. Alternatively, IBM approaches can be classified as sharp interface or diffuse
interface methods. It is worth noting that there are additional methods that are specific to a certain class of
64 problems. These are the immersed interface method [41] and the family of embedded boundary method [42]
for viscous flows and FSI. The interested reader is referred to [43, 44, 45, 46] and the references cited therein
66 for comprehensive reviews of the IBM method and their applications. Recently, a comprehensive convergence
analysis with regard to the spatial and temporal resolution is presented by Zhou and Balachandar [47]. A
68 systematic study on the convergence of IBM and an overset grid method is performed by Vreman [48].

In recent years, the volume penalization method [40, 49, 50] has attracted a lot of attention due to
70 its robustness, simplicity and proofs of convergence [40, 45]. It follows a basic physical intuition that the
solid wall can be modelled as a porous medium with vanishing diffusivity [51]. A characteristic or mask
72 function χ is introduced which is 1 in the solid domain and 0 elsewhere. A source or penalty function is
introduced and is active in the solid domain. The penalization source term is designed to impose the desired
74 boundary conditions. When compared with the other IBM approaches, the reconstruction procedure and the
distribution of the source term are not needed, thus largely reducing the computational cost. The extension to
76 moving boundary problems based on volume penalization is also straightforward. The penalization method
can be traced back to the works of Courant [52] who introduced such an approach to transform constrained
78 optimization problems into problems free of constraints. The volume penalization method for the Navier-
Stokes was first proposed by Arquis and Caltagirone [53] to simulate the natural convection flow inside
80 a fluid-porous cavity where a Brinkman type penalization was introduced to the momentum equation.

Rigorous proofs of the convergence have been given by Angot et al. [40] and Carbou and Fabrie [54] where it was proven that, as the penalization parameter η approaches 0, the solution of the penalized Navier-Stokes equations will converge to the solution of the Navier-Stokes equations with no-slip boundary conditions (Dirichlet type). Thereafter, volume penalization has been extended to allow Neumann boundary conditions [51, 55] and Robin boundary conditions [56] using finite volume and pseudo spectral methods. Recently, the volume penalization method for spatially varying Neumann and Robin boundary conditions was studied by Thirumalaisamy et al. [57]. The volume penalization method has also been applied to compressible flows by Liu and Vasilyev [58], Brown-Dymkoski et al. [50], Abgrall et al. [49] and Abalakin et al. [59]. The method has been successfully used for complex flow problems such as flapping wings [60], two-phase flow [61], FSI [62], thermal flows [63], and turbulent rotating flows [64]. The comparison between direct forcing method and the penalization method has been studied by Piquet et al. [65], where it was found that the volume-penalization method is a suitable and a possibly competitive IBM method for viscous flows in terms of predictive performance, accuracy and computational cost. A review of volume penalization method for numerical simulation of complex flows is given by Schneider [45].

Despite the amount of publication devoted to volume penalization, this technique has not been studied with the high-order methods. It does not need to treat complicated cell cuts, and is easy to be extended to moving boundaries. Therefore, it is worth investigating the performance of high-order methods with volume penalization method, which is the aim and novelty of the present work. The high-order method adopted in the current study is based on the FR approach [6, 24, 25]. It provides a differential framework for discontinuous finite element schemes, which is a unifying framework for high-order methods and can recover existing high-order schemes. Volume penalization is used to impose the no-slip boundary condition within the solid body. The present approach allows locally refining the solution near the wall to improve both the accuracy and the smoothness of the solution, using local p-refinement of the FR scheme. Increasing the polynomial order also leads to improved solution for moving boundary simulation. To the authors' knowledge, these advantages have not been reported in previous works about IBM.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 gives an introduction of the Navier-Stokes equations. Section 3 presents the high-order FR method for general conservation laws. Section 4 details the volume penalization method used in the present study for IBM treatment, along with the method for surface data reconstruction and the handling of moving boundary. The proposed method is tested in Section 5, where cases with increasing complexity are shown. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2. The Governing Equations

The governing equations for a compressible viscous fluid are written as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{U} denotes the vector of conserved variables, where $\mathbf{U} = (\rho, \rho u, \rho v, \rho w, E)^T$. ρ is the density, u , v and w are the velocity components and E is the total energy. The equations are closed by the ideal gas equation-of-state:

$$E = \frac{P}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{1}{2}\rho(u^2 + v^2 + w^2), \quad (2)$$

where P is the static pressure and γ is the ratio of specific heats. The flux vectors \mathbf{F}_x , \mathbf{F}_y , \mathbf{F}_z contain the inviscid and viscous fluxes and are written as

$$\mathbf{F}_x = \begin{pmatrix} \rho u \\ \rho u^2 + P \\ \rho uv \\ \rho uw \\ u(E + P) \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \tau_{xx} \\ \tau_{xy} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ u\tau_{xx} + v\tau_{xy} + w\tau_{xz} + q_x \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{F}_{x,ivc} + \mathbf{F}_{x,usc}, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_y = \begin{pmatrix} \rho v \\ \rho uv \\ \rho v^2 + P \\ \rho vw \\ v(E + P) \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \tau_{yx} \\ \tau_{yy} \\ \tau_{yz} \\ u\tau_{yx} + v\tau_{yy} + w\tau_{yz} + q_y \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{F}_{y,ivc} + \mathbf{F}_{y,usc}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_z = \begin{pmatrix} \rho w \\ \rho uw \\ \rho vw \\ \rho w^2 + P \\ w(E + P) \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \tau_{zx} \\ \tau_{zy} \\ \tau_{zz} \\ u\tau_{zx} + v\tau_{zy} + w\tau_{zz} + q_z \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{F}_{z,ivc} + \mathbf{F}_{z,usc}. \quad (5)$$

In these equations, $\tau_{ij} = \mu(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} - \frac{2}{3}\delta_{ij}\frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_k})$ is the viscous stress tensor with μ denoting the dynamic viscosity. The heat flux vector $\nabla \mathbf{q}$ is given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial x_i} = \lambda \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i}, \quad (6)$$

112 where λ is the thermal conductivity and T is the static temperature. The equations are solved in non-
 113 dimensional form with the introduction of the Prandtl number $\text{Pr} = \mu \frac{C_p}{\lambda}$, the Reynolds number $Re =$
 114 $\rho_{ref} V_{ref} L_{ref} / \mu_{ref}$ and the Mach number $M = V_{ref} / \sqrt{\gamma R_{gas} T_{ref}}$, with C_p being the specific heat capacity
 115 at constant pressure and R_{gas} being the gas constant. Finally, V_{ref} , L_{ref} , T_{ref} are reference velocity, length
 116 and temperature, respectively. The discretization of these equations with the FR method is described next.

3. The Flux Reconstruction Method

118 Flux reconstruction is a high-order framework which unifies a number of other high-order methods like
 119 the SD method and the nodal DG method. FR was first introduced by Hyunh for advection [6] and diffusion
 120 [24] equations. This method is detailed below. Consider the following hyperbolic system of conservation
 laws:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{F}_{ivc} + \mathbf{F}_{vsc}) &= \mathbf{S}, \\ \mathbf{Q} - \nabla \mathbf{U} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

122 where \mathbf{F}_{ivc} , \mathbf{F}_{vsc} , \mathbf{S} refer to the inviscid flux, viscous flux and the source term. These vectors are functions of
 the solution \mathbf{U} and its gradient $\mathbf{Q} = \nabla \mathbf{U}$. The space dimension is defined as \mathcal{D} . After the space discretization,

124 the computational domain Ω is divided into N_c distinct cells. In each cell, the discrete solution \mathbf{U}_i^δ is locally
 126 approximated by a polynomial of degree P , defined at N_p solution points. In addition, the flux at each
 interface of an element is approximated by a polynomial of degree $P + 1$, defined at N_f flux points on the
 element interface. An isoparametric spatial mapping $\mathcal{M} : \mathbf{x} \rightarrow \boldsymbol{\xi}$ is defined to transform physical coordinates
 128 of the solution and flux points to reference coordinates [66, 67]. In the present study, we utilize a standard
 tensor-product formulation with a Legendre polynomial basis to define the polynomial interpolation. The
 130 solution and flux points are located at the Gaussian quadrature points. Note that another popular choice
 of these points is based on the Gauss-Lobatto quadrature rule (including element end-points). A schematic
 132 representation of solution and flux points for a quadrangle mesh with polynomial order $P = 2$ is shown in
 Figure 1:

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the solution and the flux points for a quadrangle mesh with polynomial order $P = 2$. Solution and flux points are located at the Gaussian quadrature points. Note that the flux points are co-located between the two elements at the interface. Discontinuous fluxes are computed at solution points (denoted by $\delta\mathbf{D}$), while interpolated, common and interaction, as well as correction fluxes are computed at flux points (denoted by $\delta\mathbf{F}$, $\delta\mathbf{I}$, $\delta\mathbf{C}$, respectively).

134 The standard flux reconstruction process for the general conservation law can include seven stages [68]
 as follows:

136 1. Getting the interpolated solution at flux points. The interpolated solution at the flux point $\boldsymbol{\xi}^{\delta\mathbf{F}}$ is
 given by the following polynomial interpolation:

$$\mathbf{U}^{\delta\mathbf{D}}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{U}_i^{\delta\mathbf{D}} \mathcal{I}_i^P(\boldsymbol{\xi}), \quad (8)$$

138 where \mathcal{I}_i^P refers to the nodal basis function defined at each solution point with polynomials of degree P , and
 $\mathbf{U}_i^{\delta\mathbf{D}}$ is the solution at the i th solution point.

140 2. Obtaining the common solution at the flux point, which is computed from the left and right interpolated
 solutions. The Local Discontinuous Galerkin (LDG) scheme is chosen for the common solution:

$$\mathbf{U}_{f,j}^{\delta\mathbf{I}} = \{\!\!\{ \mathbf{U}_{f,j}^{\delta\mathbf{F}} \}\!\!\} - \beta \cdot [\![\mathbf{U}_{f,j}^{\delta\mathbf{F}}]\!], \quad (9)$$

where β refers to an upwinding parameter, $\delta\mathbf{F}$ and $\delta\mathbf{I}$ refers to the interpolated flux and the common flux at
 flux points, respectively. $\{\!\!\{ \cdot \}\!\!\}$ and $[\![\cdot]\!]$ compute the mean and jump values of the interpolated solution. The
 correction solution is subsequently given as:

$$\mathbf{U}_{f,j}^{\delta\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{U}_{f,j}^{\delta\mathbf{I}} - \mathbf{U}_{f,j}^{\delta\mathbf{F}}. \quad (10)$$

142 3. Computing the gradient of solution \mathbf{Q} at the solution point from the correction solution $\mathbf{U}^{\delta C}$ and the discrete solution $\mathbf{U}^{\delta D}$:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}^{\delta D} = \tilde{\nabla} \mathbf{U} = \tilde{\nabla} \mathbf{U}^{\delta D} + \tilde{\nabla} \mathbf{U}^{\delta C}, \quad (11)$$

144 where the discrete gradient $\tilde{\nabla} \mathbf{U}^{\delta D}$ in the reference space is computed from the gradient of the discrete solution $\mathbf{U}^{\delta D}$:

$$\tilde{\nabla} \mathbf{U}^{\delta D}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{U}_i^{\delta D} \tilde{\nabla} \mathcal{I}_i^P(\boldsymbol{\xi}). \quad (12)$$

146 The corrected gradient $\tilde{\nabla} \mathbf{U}^{\delta C}$ is computed by transforming the correction solution from the flux points to the solution points. This is achieved by the correction function:

$$\tilde{\nabla} \mathbf{U}^{\delta C}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{f=1}^{N_{face}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_f} \tilde{\nabla} \mathcal{C}_{f,j}^{P+1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \cdot \mathbf{U}_{f,j}^{\delta C}, \quad (13)$$

148 where the function $\mathcal{C}_{f,j}^{P+1}$ is the correction function, which is of polynomial order $P + 1$. The final gradient is obtained by transforming the values from the reference to the physical space.

150 4. Computing the discrete flux at each solution point based on the solution and gradient (obtained from the first three stages). The inviscid and viscous flux at each solution point is defined by the same polynomial
152 interpolation with degree P :

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{ivc}}^{\delta D}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{F}_{\text{ivc},i}^{\delta D} \mathcal{I}_i^P(\boldsymbol{\xi}), \quad \mathbf{F}_{\text{vsc}}^{\delta D}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{F}_{\text{vsc},i}^{\delta D} \mathcal{I}_i^P(\boldsymbol{\xi}). \quad (14)$$

The interpolated fluxes $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ivc}}^{\delta F}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{\text{vsc}}^{\delta F}$ at flux points are obtained from the above formulation.

154 5. Obtaining the interaction flux $\mathbf{F}^{\delta I}$ at each flux point. (Again, shared by two neighboring elements at the common interface.) This flux is approximated by a Riemann solver $\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{U}_{f,j,-}^{\delta F}, \mathbf{Q}_{f,j,-}^{\delta F}, \mathbf{U}_{f,j,+}^{\delta F}, \mathbf{Q}_{f,j,+}^{\delta F})$.
156 For the inviscid flux, the Rusanov flux is used. The viscous part of the interaction flux is obtained by the LDG approach computed as:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{vsc},f,j}^{\delta I} = \mathbf{F}_{\text{vsc},f,j}^{\delta F} + \tau \cdot \llbracket \mathbf{U}_{f,j}^{\delta F} \rrbracket + \beta \cdot \llbracket \mathbf{F}_{\text{vsc},f,j}^{\delta F} \rrbracket, \quad (15)$$

158 where the τ is the parameter controlling the jump of the solution, and β is the upwinding parameter defined previously. For LDG approach, a combination of $\beta = 0.5$ and $\tau = 0.1$ is used here, in order to promote
160 compactness of the FR scheme in multiple dimensions [68].

162 6. Computing the flux correction term at the flux point. This term is constructed from the interaction flux, the interpolated flux and the correction function. The correction flux is the difference between the interaction and the interpolated fluxes:

$$\mathbf{F}_{f,j}^{\delta C} = \mathbf{F}_{f,j}^{\delta I} - \mathbf{F}_{f,j}^{\delta F}. \quad (16)$$

164 The corrected divergence of flux correction term is transformed from the flux difference at the flux points

to the solution points through the correction function:

$$\tilde{\nabla} \cdot \mathbf{F}^{\delta C}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{D}} \sum_{f=1}^{N_{face}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_f} \tilde{\nabla}_k \mathcal{C}_{f,j}^{P+1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \cdot \mathbf{F}_{f,j,k}^{\delta C}, \quad (17)$$

166 where k refers to the spatial direction index.

168 7. Calculating the divergence of the continuous flux from the local discrete flux divergence and the corrected divergence at the solution points:

$$\tilde{U}_t^{\delta D} = -\tilde{\nabla} \cdot \mathbf{F} = -\tilde{\nabla} \cdot \mathbf{F}^{\delta D} - \tilde{\nabla} \cdot \mathbf{F}^{\delta C} = -\sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{D}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \tilde{\nabla}_k \mathcal{I}_i^P(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \cdot \mathbf{F}_{i,k}^{\delta D} - \sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{D}} \sum_{f=1}^{N_{face}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_f} \tilde{\nabla}_k \mathcal{C}_{f,j}^{P+1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \cdot \mathbf{F}_{f,j,k}^{\delta C}. \quad (18)$$

170 Finally, the divergence of flux needs to be transformed into the physical space. Once the divergence of continuous flux is obtained, the equation can be advanced in time by any explicit or implicit time-marching method. The governing equation can be discretized as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{U}}{dt} = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{U}), \quad (19)$$

172 where $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{U})$ refers to the residual of the equation, which is a function of \mathbf{U} . The boundary conditions, like the far-field characteristic boundary condition, are imposed in a weak-Riemann formulation following Mengaldo et al. [69]. The ghost state from the boundary side of the face is given from the boundary condition, while the flux is calculated by a Riemann solver. Moreover, the performance of flux reconstruction depends on six factors [68], including the location of solution and flux point, the Riemann solvers used for computing the common solution values and the interaction fluxes, and the form of the correction functions for solution and flux values. For the time marching method, we use the classic TVD Runge-Kutta explicit time marching method. Equations of time integration are

$$\mathbf{U}^* = \mathbf{U}^n + \Delta t \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{U}^n), \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{**} = \frac{1}{4}[3\mathbf{U}^n + \mathbf{U}^* + \Delta t \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{U}^*)], \quad (21)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{n+1} = \frac{1}{3}[\mathbf{U}^n + 2\mathbf{U}^{**} + 2\Delta t \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{U}^{**})], \quad (22)$$

180 where Δt denotes the time step, and n is the present time index. Note that when the IBM source term is present, a splitting approach can be used to handle the stiffness of the source term. In the current explicit time marching approach, the simulation starts from a constant flow field, where transient acoustic waves exist when the simulation starts. To handle such problems, we run the simulation for a sufficiently long time, where the final non-dimensional time is usually set to around 100. Simulation of moving boundaries will also start from this meaningful flow field. Furthermore, when a more efficient time integration method is considered, e.g., low-storage fourth-order Runge-Kutta approach [5], the maximal time step allowed for the simulation can be larger.

188 **4. Immersed Boundary Method**

The basic idea of IBM is to impose boundary conditions to the non body-fitted mesh with proper numerical treatment. Volume penalization is a typical method, which imposes boundary condition through penalizing the velocity of solution points in the solid body. This method is easy to understand and implement with rigorous theoretical foundation, therefore it is selected for the present study.

194 *4.1. The volume penalization method*

The volume penalization method imposes boundary conditions by introducing penalization source terms to the governing equations. In this approach, a mask function which distinguishes between the fluid region Ω_f and the solid region Ω_s is defined first:

$$\chi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_s \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (23)$$

This mask function is used to determine whether the IBM force should be imposed to the current solution point [49, 50]. For moving boundaries, $\chi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is time-dependent. It should be noted that this definition of mask function will lead to a sharp jump of source term between the solid and fluid points near the boundary, which may incur spurious oscillations (or Gibbs phenomena) of the hydrodynamic forces on moving obstacles [60]. In addition, for static obstacle, this sharp mask function may also lead to oscillations of flow variables near the wall. These oscillations can be reduced by smoothing the mask function, which will smooth the transition between the solid and fluid points, thus allowing smaller penalty forces for solution points near the wall. This strategy is also tested and will be discussed in Appendix B. The volume penalization method for a high-order, Cartesian mesh is illustrated in Fig. 2. All solution points, covered by the solid region, need to be penalized to impose the boundary condition.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of volume penalization for high-order method. The computational domain is discretized by the Cartesian grid. Solution points defining the high-order polynomial are represented by black circles. The polynomial order for the Cartesian grid is $P = 2$. The solid body Ω_s is highlighted in the red region.

The Navier-Stokes equations with IBM treatment is written as:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{RHS} + \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}), \quad (24)$$

where \mathbf{S} refers to the IBM source term. \mathbf{RHS} refers to the right hand side term of the Navier-Stokes equations

$$\mathbf{RHS} = -\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_z}{\partial z}\right). \quad (25)$$

Considering the Dirichlet boundary condition for velocity $\mathbf{u}_s = (u_s, v_s, w_s)^T$ inside the solid body, the source term is written as:

$$\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}) = \frac{\chi}{\eta} \times \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \rho u_s - \rho u \\ \rho v_s - \rho v \\ \rho w_s - \rho w \\ \frac{\rho}{2}(u_s^2 + v_s^2 + w_s^2) - \frac{\rho}{2}(u^2 + v^2 + w^2) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (26)$$

where η denotes the penalization parameter for volume penalization. When no-slip boundary condition is considered, the condition $\mathbf{u}_s = (0, 0, 0)^T$ will be imposed. These penalization terms follow the formulation in [49] to impose boundary conditions of adiabatic walls. However, this formulation also allows nonuniform Dirichlet conditions when additional source term for temperature needs to be considered [49]. Generally, the penalization parameter η should be sufficiently small to ensure high accuracy. However, small η value will lead to very stiff source terms that limit the time step. In practice, it is suggested to set the penalization parameter equal to the explicit time step Δt [62]. The same guideline has also been recommended in the context of multiphase FSI in recent works [70, 71]. More discussions on the guideline will be given in Sec. 4.6. The above equation can also be used for moving bodies, where the solid velocity is updated based on the equations of motion.

The governing equation Eq. 24 is marched in time by combining the operator splitting method and the TVD Runge-Kutta method. Due to the stiffness of the source term, we use the second-order Strang splitting [72] approach to add the source term. As discussed by Piquet et al. [65], with Strang splitting, penalization terms are computed exactly for the momentum and energy equations. At time step n , the following sequence of operations is performed:

$$\text{step 1: } \frac{\mathbf{U}_1 - \mathbf{U}^n}{\Delta t_1} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}_1), \Delta t_1 = \Delta t/2, \mathbf{U}_{1,0} = \mathbf{U}_n, \quad (27)$$

$$\text{step 2: } \frac{\mathbf{U}_2 - \mathbf{U}_1}{\Delta t_2} = \mathbf{RHS}(\mathbf{U}_2), \Delta t_2 = \Delta t, \mathbf{U}_{2,0} = \mathbf{U}_1, \quad (28)$$

$$\text{step 3: } \frac{\mathbf{U}^{n+1} - \mathbf{U}_2}{\Delta t_3} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}^{n+1}), \Delta t_3 = \Delta t/2, \mathbf{U}_0^{n+1} = \mathbf{U}_2. \quad (29)$$

Currently, the third-order TVD Runge-Kutta method is used in step 2 to perform explicit time marching. In step 1 and step 3, when adding the source term, both implicit or explicit forcing methods can be considered. The implicit treatment of the forcing term, which is a new approach proposed in this paper, can lead to better numerical stability allowing a smaller penalization parameter. This is beneficial for the volume penalization method due to very stiff source terms. We have observed that for a given explicit time step / CFL condition, the implicit forcing allows to reduce the penalization parameter about one or two orders of magnitude compared to the one necessary in an explicit forcing method. Similar implicit treatments

for volume penalization have also been proposed in [59] for compressible and in [70, 71] for incompressible
 230 multiphase flows. Explicit and implicit approaches are detailed here:

Explicit forcing : The explicit formulation is simply given as:

$$\frac{\mathbf{U}_1 - \mathbf{U}^n}{\Delta t_1} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}^n), \quad (30)$$

$$\mathbf{U}_1 = \mathbf{U}^n + \Delta t_1 \cdot \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}^n). \quad (31)$$

Implicit forcing : For implicit implementation of the penalty method, the backward Euler method with first-order Taylor expansion leads to the following formulation

$$\frac{\mathbf{U}_1 - \mathbf{U}^n}{\Delta t_1} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}^n) + \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}^n)}{\partial \mathbf{U}} (\mathbf{U}_1 - \mathbf{U}^n). \quad (32)$$

After some manipulation, the following equation is obtained:

$$\left(\mathbf{I} - \Delta t_1 \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{U}^n) \right) \mathbf{U}_1 = \mathbf{U}^n + \Delta t_1 \left(\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}^n) - \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{U}^n) \mathbf{U}^n \right), \quad (33)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. From Eq. 26, the Jacobian matrix of the IBM force term, is then derived as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \mathbf{U}} = -\frac{1}{\eta} \times \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{2}(u^2 + v^2 + w^2) & u & v & w & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (34)$$

Therefore, the inversion of matrix $\mathbf{I} - \Delta t_1 \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{U}^n)$ can be derived analytically

$$\left(\mathbf{I} - \Delta t_1 \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{U}^n) \right)^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\eta}{\Delta t_1 + \eta} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\eta}{\Delta t_1 + \eta} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\eta}{\Delta t_1 + \eta} & 0 \\ \frac{\Delta t_1}{2\eta}(u^2 + v^2 + w^2) & -\frac{\Delta t_1 u}{\Delta t_1 + \eta} & -\frac{\Delta t_1 v}{\Delta t_1 + \eta} & -\frac{\Delta t_1 w}{\Delta t_1 + \eta} & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (35)$$

By substituting Eq. 34 and Eq. 35 into Eq. 33, the implicit forcing problem is solved.

232 4.2. Boundary representation and mask function

Representation of solid boundaries is a crucial aspect of IBM approaches. It serves for two main purposes:
 234 1) the definition of mask function. For general geometries where a simple shape function cannot be found, the mask function χ should be determined by effective methods to identify whether the present solution
 236 point is inside or outside the solid body. 2) the computation of aerodynamic coefficients. This depends on how the surface of obstacle is discretized, since the flow quantities on the surface need to be interpolated

238 from solutions of its surrounding solution points, and the surface normal and area are also needed for force
 computation.

240 The discretization of immersed boundary should be flexible enough to handle complex geometries. In the
 present study, we choose to use a set of Lagrangian marker points to represent the solid boundary, defined
 242 as immersed boundary (IB) points. The marker points are connected by linear elements, i.e., line segments
 in two dimensions and triangular elements in three dimensions. Calculations of the geometrical quantities,
 244 including the surface normal, the interpolation stencil for data reconstruction, and the surface distance,
 can be performed efficiently with this representation [73, 39]. Developing algorithm to compute the mask
 246 function also depends on such discretization strategy.

Figure 3: Determination of mask function for general geometries, based on (a) ray casting and (b) the simplified approach used in the present study. The polynomial order for the Cartesian grid is $P = 2$.

For simple geometries like a cylinder, a sphere or an airfoil, analytical shape functions exist and can be
 248 used to define the mask function, as listed in Appendix A. However, in order to handle other geometries whose
 shape function is difficult to obtain, we still need an algorithm to compute the mask function. Therefore,
 250 in the present work, a method to get the mask function for general shapes, rather than using the analytical
 function, has been developed. This method takes an algorithm to identify whether the present solution
 252 point is inside or outside the solid body. It relies on solving a typical 'point in polygon' (PIP)¹ problem in
 computational geometry [74]. PIP problem refers to a set of problems, where one needs to determine whether
 254 a given point in the plane lies inside, outside, or on the boundary of a polygon. One common approach is
 ray casting. Ray casting approach generates a ray starting from the point of interest following any direction,
 256 and tests how many times a ray intersects the edges of the polygon. If the point is outside the polygon, the
 ray will intersect the edges an even number of times. On the contrary, if the point is inside the polygon,
 258 the ray will intersect the edges an odd number of times. Schematic illustration of the ray casting method is
 shown in Fig. 3a.

260 In practice, the ray casting method can be implemented in multiple ways. We take a simplified method to
 achieve this. For any solution point in the computation domain, we first define those points that lie outside
 262 the bounding box of the surface (i.e., the box formed by coordinates of the rectangular border that fully
 encloses the solid body) to be the fluid points. For other solution points lie inside the bounding box, we will

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Point_in_polygon

264 draw a line along y-axis direction (in 2D) or z-axis (in 3D), as shown in Fig. 3b. After that, the maximum
 and minimum intercepts in y coordinate (2D) or in z coordinate (3D) are identified. If the corresponding
 266 coordinate of the solution point lies within this range, we define this point as the solid point and set its
 mask to 1. From an implementation point of view, this can be achieved by firstly looking for the nearest
 268 IB points along x direction (2D) or x-y plane (3D). After that, the minimum and maximum values of these
 points in y coordinate or z coordinate are easily obtained, and the comparison is subsequently performed.
 270 To achieve this approach, the boundary should be sufficiently resolved by the IB points, in order to make
 sure the accuracy of neighboring search involved in getting the mask function. A limitation of this method
 272 is that it is only applicable to convex geometry. For non-convex geometry, more than two intercepts exist.
 The ray tracing method can be applied to such cases to check how many times the ray intersect the edges
 274 along the y or z direction. However, the present approach still works well for the test cases considered in this
 work. In addition, an alternative approach to solve the PIP problem is to construct signed distance function
 276 from surface triangulation of the body, and then simply set the mask function in terms of the signed distance
 function [75].

278 4.3. Treatment for moving boundaries

This subsection introduces the treatment of moving boundaries (with rigid motion) for the volume penal-
 280 ization method. When the boundary moves, the mask function and the velocity at each solution point should
 be updated accordingly. The basic idea of updating the mask for each solution point is to first recover the
 282 position of this point relative to the original solid body at $t = 0$ (in the non-inertial reference frame), then
 determine the mask value based on the recovered position and the mask function defined for the original
 284 solid body $\chi(\mathbf{x}, 0)$. The velocity is updated based on the rigid motion equation of the obstacle.

Figure 4: Schematic illustration of an airfoil free to move in translation and rotation directions, with chord length c . a , b and θ are displacements in x and y directions, and the pitching angle, respectively. This definition is applicable to any rigid body.

For the cases considered in this study, i.e., a two-dimensional solid body with rigid motion, the translation
 286 in x-axis and y-axis directions, and the rotation motions are included [60]. These displacements are defined
 respectively as a , b , and θ , following positive x and y direction, and clockwise rotation direction. The initial
 288 rotation axis at $t = 0$ is given as (x_r, y_r) . Although the present treatment of moving boundaries is not limited
 to any specific geometry, the schematic illustration of a moving airfoil is shown in Fig. 4 as an example.
 290 When the boundary is moving, as the first step, the coordinates are translated into the reference coordinates
 in the non-inertial reference frame:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{x} \\ \tilde{y} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x - a(t) - x_r \\ y - b(t) - y_r \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} x_r \\ y_r \end{pmatrix}. \quad (36)$$

292 The mask for any solution point placed in (x, y) is determined based on the transformed coordinates in
the non-inertial reference frame, through substituting \tilde{x} and \tilde{y} into the original mask function $\chi(\mathbf{x}, 0)$. To
294 achieve this, we need to save the original mask function in the whole simulation process. This can be easily
done when a geometry with analytical shape function is used. For general geometries, the mask function
296 based on ray-tracing method can be encapsulated into a wrapper, which can be saved at the beginning of
the simulation. Note that recovering the transformed coordinates remains to be a point-wise operation.
298 Therefore, even in parallel environments, this operation does not require additional cost of communication.
The solid velocity at each solution point is subsequently updated as follows, which is also a point-wise
300 operation:

$$\dot{x} = \dot{a}(t) + \dot{\theta}(t)(y - b(t) - y_r), \quad (37)$$

$$\dot{y} = \dot{b}(t) - \dot{\theta}(t)(x - a(t) - x_r). \quad (38)$$

It should be pointed out that this method is not applicable to flexible structures, e.g., when the boundary
302 geometry changes with time. In such cases, recovering the position of solution point in the non-inertial
reference frame becomes difficult. A solution is to redefine the mask function at each time step based on
304 the updated position of surface points. The velocity of solution points immersed in the solid should also be
approximated numerically [62]. These operations will require additional computational burden compared to
306 the present problem. In addition, if the movement is too big in one time step, there can be a loss of mass
due to the fast transition between fluid and solid state. Some strategies can be considered to handle such
308 problems [39, 76], which is worth investigating in the future.

4.4. Surface data reconstruction

310 The reconstruction of data on the solid surface is an important aspect to obtain the distribution of
quantities of interest (e.g., pressure and friction force) from simulation results. The integrated aerodynamic
312 coefficients, like lift and drag, rely on these reconstructed quantities. For original IBM approaches based
on delta functions, spurious oscillations exist for surface stresses, which often lead to nonphysical temporal
314 oscillations of the integrated forces. This can be improved by using filtering strategies [77] or by a moving
control volume approach [78]. For other IBM approaches, the basic idea to get the surface quantity for each
316 surface point (i.e., IB point) is to perform interpolation based on data of surrounding solution points.

Figure 5: Different locations of solid surface point within a numerical element with polynomial order $P = 2$. Blue circle is the surface marker point. Red region is the solid region. Black points are solution points inside the element.

In the high-order framework, it is straightforward to consider using the high-order polynomial defined
318 in each element to perform data reconstruction. The procedure in such cases is very simple: 1) find the
element where the current IB point lies; 2) compute the reference coordinate of this IB point in the present

320 element; 3) apply the polynomial interpolation scheme at this reference coordinate. This method, however,
 322 has some potential drawbacks that lead to inaccuracy. This is mainly due to the fact that in most of cases,
 such interpolation formula will involve solution points immersed in the solid, which usually have nonphysical
 324 values. The schematic illustration for this problem is given in Fig. 5, where in all situations, nonphysical
 values at the solid solution point will be involved in interpolation. To visualize how it works, a comparison
 between polynomial interpolation and the data reconstruction method used in the present study is detailed
 326 in Appendix C, illustrating the failure of directly using high-order polynomial for data reconstruction.

Other than polynomial interpolation, an alternative method is to interpolate the data from several nearest
 328 solution points. Compared with interpolation based on the high-order polynomial, it has more flexibility to
 select the interpolation points, without involving the solid solution points with nonphysical values. Here,
 330 the interpolation methods described in [79] are followed, and are adapted to the high-order framework.
 In general, the interpolation framework in [79] is based on the inverse distance between the IB point and
 332 the interpolation point. Candidate interpolation points are chosen from the nearest fluid points around
 the IB point. The value and gradient of conservative variables are interpolated. To compute aerodynamic
 334 coefficients, the pressure and the shear stress are subsequently obtained from the interpolated variables. In
 particular, the Inverse Distance Weight at Interpolation Point (IDW-IP) method is used for interpolation in
 336 the present study.

For standard IDW method, the inverse distance between each surface point and the solution point is used
 338 as a weighting factor to compute the value of any variable, as shown below

$$U_{IB} = \frac{\sum_i U_i / d_i}{\sum_i 1 / d_i}, \quad (39)$$

where U_i and d_i refer to the solution vector and distance to surface point of the i th. For IDW-IP method,
 340 following [80], we first define the interpolation point (IP) as a virtual point close to a specific IB point
 that lies along the normal of that point. Here the normal can be computed efficiently based on the surface
 342 representation method described in Sec. 4.2. The distance of IP to the IB point is defined as

$$d_{IP} = \frac{\sum_i d_{2,i} / d_{1,i}}{\sum_i 1 / d_{1,i}}, \quad (40)$$

where d_1 is the perpendicular distance from any solution point to the surface normal of the IB point, while
 344 d_2 is the projection of the distance from the solution point to the IB point along the surface normal. These
 points and distances are illustrated in Fig. 6.

346 Like the IDW method, the data is interpolated from the surrounding solution points but with d_1 as the
 distance (see Fig. 6). Since this IDW-IP method considers the data interpolation along the wall normal
 348 direction, it also can be extended to the velocity reconstruction required in the development of wall models
 for turbulent flow simulation [81, 82]. From the above equation, the interpolation formulation becomes [79]:

$$U_{IP} = \frac{\sum_i U_i / d_{1,i}}{\sum_i 1 / d_{1,i}}. \quad (41)$$

350 Interested readers can refer to [79] for more details. After extensive testing, we found a good balance
 between accuracy and efficiency is to choose the nearest $2N_p \sim 3N_p$ flow points, where N_p refers to the
 352 number of solution points for near-wall elements. The integrated aerodynamic loads, including the lift and
 drag coefficients, is obtained from the reconstructed data at IB points. In particular, surface pressure P and

Figure 6: Schematic illustration of data reconstruction method on a Cartesian grid with polynomial order $P = 2$.

354 shear stress τ_{ij} need to be reconstructed. The lift and drag coefficients are given as:

$$C_l = \frac{1}{(1/2)\rho_\infty U_\infty l} \int_{\partial S} (\tau_y \mathbf{n} - P_y) dS, \quad (42)$$

$$C_d = \frac{1}{(1/2)\rho_\infty U_\infty l} \int_{\partial S} (\tau_x \mathbf{n} - P_x) dS, \quad (43)$$

where l is the characteristic length. In addition, the boundary representation discussed in Sec. 4.2 allows getting the surface normal and area efficiently. For an accurate integration of aerodynamic forces, the distribution of surface points to represent the boundary should be sufficiently dense.

358 The implementation of data reconstruction (IDW-IP method) in the high-order framework is as follows:
 1) locate the element where the current IB point lies; 2) find neighboring elements of this element (and neighbors of the neighboring element) and get the coordinates and masks for all the solution points in these
 360 elements; 3) compute the distance of all candidate solution points to the IB point, and rank the points
 362 based on the distance in increasing order; 4) select the points according to the rank, and discard the points immersed in the solid, until the preset number of stencil points is reached; 5) compute the distance d_1 for
 364 all candidate stencil points, and compute the weighting coefficients for each stencil point based on Eq. 41.

4.5. Overview of the algorithm

366 The proposed IBM approach based on volume penalization and high-order FR can be summarized in Fig. 7. Overall, the following procedures are needed:

368 (1) Import the background mesh and IBM geometry. The geometrical information is extracted from the IBM marker points, including the surface normal and surface area. The distance to the surface is also needed
 370 if the mask needs to be smoothed Appendix B. The reconstruction stencil is computed for each marker point, respectively. For the static boundary, these operations are only performed once in the simulation.

372 (2) At each time step, perform the first splitting step, the Runge-Kutta explicit time integration, and the second splitting step accordingly.

374 (3) When the solid body is moving, additional operations are required after every time step (or every several time steps) to update the information. The solid displacement is first updated based on the prescribed motion function. This displacement is then used to update the mask and the velocity for each solution point,
 376 based on the method in Sec. 4.3. To evaluate the aerodynamic coefficients under moving boundaries, both

Figure 7: Flow chart of the proposed method.

378 the surface IB points and its normal vector are updated. With the updated position of IB points, we also
 need to update the stencil and the weight for data reconstruction.

380 4.6. Discussions on error estimate and selection of penalization parameter

One of advantages of the volume penalization method over other IBM approaches is that rigorous proofs
 382 of the convergence have been given [40, 54]. Therefore, the numerical error introduced from the penal-
 ization term can be controlled a-priori [50]. The error of the numerical solution of the penalized problem
 384 corresponding to the original problem includes two parts [62], the penalization error and the discretization
 error:

$$\|u^{exact} - u_\eta^N\| \leq \|u^{exact} - u_\eta\| + \|u_\eta - u_\eta^N\|, \quad (44)$$

where u^{exact} is the exact analytical solution of the governing equations, u_η and u_η^N are the exact and
 numerical solution of the penalized equations. $\|\cdot\|$ is the norm used for quantifying the error, e.g., L_1 , L_2 or
 L_∞ norm. The first part of error is the penalization error depending on the penalization parameter [45]:

$$\|u^{exact} - u_\eta\| \propto \eta^\alpha. \quad (45)$$

386 It should be emphasized again that the physical interpretation of volume penalization is that the solid
 obstacle is assumed to be a porous medium with sufficiently small permeability η , thus the velocity of the
 388 surrounding fluid tends to be zero and vanishes at the interface. Therefore, the convergence of the solution
 of penalization method to the exact solution requires the error norm to approach zero for small penalization
 390 parameter limit, i.e., $\lim_{\eta \rightarrow 0} \|u^{exact} - u_\eta\| \rightarrow 0$. In order to achieve this, we need $\alpha > 0$. Fortunately,
 theories based on rigorous mathematics have been proposed to validate that volume penalization method
 392 satisfies this requirement. From Angot et al. [40] and Carbou and Fabrie [54], the volume penalization gives

$\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$, indicating the penalization error has a decay rate of $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{\eta})$ for Dirichlet boundary conditions. For
 394 Neumann boundary conditions, $\mathcal{O}(\eta)$ can be obtained [83].

The discretization error refers to the error between the exact solution and the numerical solution of the
 396 penalized equations. With consistent discretization and a stable numerical scheme, the discretization error
 usually follows ($\beta > 0$ and N refers to the number of grid points):

$$\|u_\eta - u_\eta^N\| \propto N^{-\beta}, \quad (46)$$

398 However, as pointed out by Schneider et al. [51, 45], the discretization error is not only determined by
 the numerical scheme, but also limited by the regularity of the solution. Regularity is characterized by the
 400 smoothness / continuity of the exact solution u_η at the boundary of the penalized problem. Therefore, the
 order of convergence β becomes the minimum order between the numerical scheme and the regularity of
 402 the exact penalized solution. For high-order method, the error of the numerical scheme can be reduced by
 performing mesh refinement (h-refinement) or increasing polynomial order (p-refinement). However, the low
 404 regularity of the solution near the wall for the penalized equation still remains a challenge to the present
 method. Another drawback for volume penalization is the so-called diffused-interface property. This is
 406 because volume penalization only determines whether the present solution lies inside or outside the solid
 body, rather than considering the exact position of boundary to preserve the sharpness of the immersed
 408 boundaries. This issue can lead to blurred descriptions of the boundaries, see discussion in [64].

From the error estimate, it is suggested to use a very small penalization parameter η to minimize the
 410 penalization error. However, small η will lead to very stiff source term, thus causing stability issues. This is
 the motivation of using splitting approach to add the IBM source term, as discussed in Sec. 4.1. In prac-
 412 tice, the penalization parameter depends on the numerical resolution, where smaller penalization parameter
 requires a smaller time step and finer resolution near the wall. When the penalization source term is treated
 414 explicitly, from the linear stability analysis [60], the time step for explicit time integration must be smaller
 than the penalization parameter $\Delta t < \eta$. This condition can be relaxed by using the Strang splitting method
 416 in the present study, and can be further relaxed with the novel implicit forcing approach introduced in Sec.
 4.1. Also in [84], the intimate coupling between Δt and η is observed, indicating the error will saturate when
 418 $\Delta t \approx \eta$. This explains why it is usually suggested to use $\Delta t = \eta$ in the volume penalization method. An
 interpretation is that the penalty term acts as a strong damping term with order η on the velocity, which
 420 has to be resolved by the time discretization scheme [62]. From a practical point of view, one can select
 the maximal Δt which allows $\Delta t = \eta$ to maintain both computational efficiency and accuracy. Note that in
 422 high-order methods, the time step Δt is determined by the Courant-Friedrichs-Levy (CFL) condition, which
 scales as the inverse of the spatial order squared [85]. Therefore a practical guideline is to fix $\Delta t = \eta$ first
 424 and determine Δt according to stability criterion.

5. Test Cases

426 In this section, the proposed IBM based on volume penalization for high-order flux reconstruction is
 validated by different test cases with increasing complexity. Analysis of one-dimensional advection-diffusion
 428 equation is firstly performed to study the convergence of the method. Simulation of flow past static obstacles
 in two and three dimensions is then shown. Finally, the capability of treating moving boundaries is validated.

430 *5.1. One-dimensional advection-diffusion equation*

The convergence behavior of the proposed method is tested in this subsection. The following one-
432 dimensional advection-diffusion is considered:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + c \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \nu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\chi}{\eta}(u - u_b) = 0, x \in [0, 1]. \quad (47)$$

The advection speed and diffusivity coefficient are chosen as $c = 0.1$ and $\nu = 0.01$, respectively. The
434 initial condition and homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions to be imposed are shown as follow:

$$u(x, 0) = \exp(5x)\sin(\pi x), u(0, t) = 0, u(1, t) = 0. \quad (48)$$

The analytical solution of this problem is given by:

$$u(x, t) = \exp(5x - t(0.01\pi^2 + 0.25))\sin(\pi x). \quad (49)$$

We choose a constant time step 1×10^{-7} to ensure time accuracy. The penalization parameter is set to
436 $\eta = \Delta t$. For the diffusion term, the β and τ used for LDG scheme are 0.5 and 0.1. We march the solution
in time to $t_{max} = 0.01$, based on the third-order TVD Runge-Kutta scheme. The convergence with respect
438 to penalization parameter is firstly tested, as shown in Fig. 8. The computational domain is discretized
by 80 elements, and 2 additional elements are extended to both sides to impose the penalized boundary
440 conditions. It should be noted that in the present problem setting, the boundary is assumed to lie exactly
at the element interface. Further studies also show that the present observations can be extended to more
442 general situations where some solution points are immersed in the solid while others are not. The solution
points in the solid are penalized by the exact solutions at two boundaries, i.e., homogeneous boundary
444 conditions $u = 0$. The error of the simulation is quantified by the L_2 error norm between the analytical
solution u and the approximated solution u_η^N within the whole fluid region. The convergence plot is given
446 in Fig. 8. It can be seen that as the penalization parameter η approaches zero, the accuracy limit of the
penalization method will be reached. The convergence rate of $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{\eta})$ is recovered at large η , which agrees
448 with the theory of penalization method for the Dirichlet problem in the continuous setting [40] [54]. In
addition, as P increases, a smaller η is required to reach the optimal accuracy. When P is larger than 1,
450 a super-convergence larger than the theoretical limit is also observed, where the convergence rate becomes
 $\mathcal{O}(\eta^{-1})$. This is different from numerical tests of low-order schemes, where $\mathcal{O}(\eta^{-0.5})$ is observed [86] [62].

The convergence with respect to the spatial resolution is then studied. To test the numerical convergence
452 in detail, we consider two situations: 1) when the analytical solution in the solid is known (e.g., Eq. (49)
is known a-priori), solutions at each solution point are penalized by its analytical solution, respectively.
454 Since the analytical solution is smooth across the boundary interface, this guarantees good regularity of the
problem. 2) when the analytical solution inside the solid is not known, but only the values at the boundary
456 are known (e.g., imposing the homogeneous Dirichlet boundary condition in Eq. (48) for all solid solution
points). In this latter case, we penalize all the solution points immersed in the solid with $u = 0$. The L_2
458 error norm in the fluid is used to quantify the error of numerical scheme. It is obvious that the latter case is
more realistic since in practice the behavior of the solutions inside the solid is unpredictable, therefore they
460 should also adopt the boundary condition at the interface.

The convergence plot of the first case is shown in Fig. 9. As shown in the figure, when the analytical
462

Figure 8: Convergence with penalization parameter η for penalized advection-diffusion equation. P is the polynomial order.

Figure 9: Convergence with the number of elements for penalized advection-diffusion equation. Solid solution points are penalized by the analytical solution. P is the polynomial order. Reference lines give the expected convergence rate of flux reconstruction scheme $N^{-(P+1)}$.

solutions for all solid points are used in the volume penalization method, an order of convergence $N^{-(P+1)}$ is recovered. This is the exact convergence rate of standard FR scheme. This indicates that the volume penalization method itself does not deteriorate the high-order convergence from high-order schemes. The same observation has also been reported in [87], where the exact velocity was imposed inside the solid region for the volume penalization approach and the expected order of accuracy was recovered. Convergence plot of the second case, which is more realistic, is shown in Fig. 10. From Fig. 10a, in the flow region far from the wall $x \in [0.2, 0.8]$, the theoretical convergence rate $N^{-(P+1)}$ can still be recovered. However, for the global fluid domain $x \in [0, 1]$, the convergence rate is reduced to approximately $\mathcal{O}(N^{-1})$ across all polynomial orders, as indicated in Fig. 10b. This is because when homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions are imposed for all solution points, the smoothness (or regularity) of the gradient across boundary cannot be guaranteed. As explained in Section 4.6, this low regularity of the solution near the wall will limit the overall convergence [51] [65]. Such limitation of convergence rate was also observed [50] [60] and discussed [45] [62] in previous works. The regularity can be improved by using a larger penalization parameter, but this will affect the accuracy near the wall [51]. In addition, due to the fact that in the flow region far from the wall, high-order accuracy can be recovered, it is preferable to perform local refinement near the wall to improve the resolution of boundary conditions, without costing too many additional degrees of freedom. Compared with the first case, it can be concluded that once the exact solution of the original equations in the solid is known, the regularity near the wall is well kept, thus better global convergence rate is recovered. Therefore, the error will only come from the numerical scheme, where the convergence of standard flux reconstruction method in the global region is retained. This case helps to investigate only the influence of spatial and temporal discretizations, and can also be used to test the correctness of code implementation with penalization method. This also directs the future development of the present method, where some strategies can be sought to maintain good regularity near the wall [88, 89], thus improving the overall accuracy and possibly retaining high-order convergence of the underlying high-order numerical framework.

(a) Order of convergence for the computational domain far from boundary $x \in [0.2, 0.8]$ (b) Order of convergence for the whole computational domain including boundary $x \in [0, 1]$

Figure 10: Convergence with number of elements for penalized advection-diffusion equation. Solid solution points are penalized by the homogeneous Dirichlet condition. P is the polynomial order. Reference lines give the expected convergence rate of flux reconstruction scheme $N^{-(P+1)}$.

5.2. Flow past a cylinder

488 The flow past a cylinder is a benchmark test case for IBM simulation. Therefore, in the present study,
it is chosen as the first test case to investigate the proposed method for the Navier-Stokes equations. The
490 Reynolds and Mach numbers are set to 40 and 0.2, where the flow remains steady. The no-slip adiabatic
wall boundary condition is considered for the wall, therefore we impose $u_s = 0$ and $v_s = 0$ in the solid. Here
492 three sets of mesh are considered. The size of rectangular computational domain is $x \in [-30D, 50D]$ and
 $y \in [-30D, 30D]$, where D is the diameter of the cylinder and is set to 1. In the square region $x \in [-D, D]$
494 and $y \in [-D, D]$, uniform grid is used. The uniform mesh size h is chosen as $0.03D$ (Mesh 1), $0.015D$
(Mesh 2) and $0.01D$ (Mesh 3), respectively. Mesh 1 is illustrated in Fig. 11. The numbers of grid points are
496 187×178 , 325×313 and 410×400 . Thanks to the inner degree of freedom given by high-order methods, the
mesh size is relatively coarse compared with existing works based on low-order methods. For example, in a
498 recent IBM work based on finite difference method [90], grid with size 800×320 is used for the same case.
With a decent mesh, the present method allows to increase the resolution based on high-order polynomial
500 approximation. We choose the polynomial order $P = 3$ for Mesh 1, $P = 2$ for Mesh 2 and Mesh 3. However,
it should be noted that for high-order methods, the total number of degrees of freedom (per equation)
502 is defined by the total number of solution points based on both the number of elements N and order of
polynomial P . For the quadrangle grid we have $N \times (P + 1)^2$ degrees of freedom. Therefore, the three
504 cases correspond to 532576, 915525 and 1476000 degrees of freedom, respectively. These numbers are still
large, but as we will show later, they can be reduced by using the local refinement capability of high-order
506 methods. The explicit time steps used for these cases are 2.5×10^{-5} , 2×10^{-5} , and 8×10^{-6} , respectively.
The penalization parameter is chosen to be equal to the time step. The characteristic boundary conditions
508 are imposed to all the far field boundaries.

Figure 11: The computational mesh (Mesh 1, locally uniform grid size $h = 0.03$)

The pressure coefficient C_p and wall spanwise vorticity ω_z are compared in Fig. 12. The results are
510 also compared with those from body-fitted simulation based on the same solver. A detailed comparison of
quantity of interest is given in Table 1. All results show good agreement on the distribution of pressure
512 coefficient. However, the prediction of spanwise vorticity is not as good as C_p . This is mainly due to
the difficulty in predicting the gradient values on the surface, since the present method only imposes the
514 constraint to the surface velocity. To solve this, refined resolution near the wall or other treatment to handle

Figure 12: Comparison of variables for flow past a cylinder at $Re = 40$ and $M = 0.2$. h and P are locally uniform grid size and the polynomial order, respectively.

Table 1: comparison of reattachment length (L/D), separation angle (θ) and drag coefficient (C_d) for flow past a cylinder

Case	L/D	θ	C_d
Dennis and Chang [91]	2.35	53.8	1.52
Fornberg [92]	2.24	55.6	1.50
Choi et al. [80]	2.21	53.6	1.49
body-fitted	2.24	51.0	1.53
Mesh 1	2.30	51.2	1.50
Mesh 2	2.30	52.0	1.51
Mesh 3	2.27	52.0	1.52

516 gradient can be a good choice. But from Table 1, good agreement with the literature is still shown, and as we increase the resolution, the results also become closer to the reference data. A typical flow snapshot is shown in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: The x -momentum field and the streamlines for flow past a cylinder at $Re = 40$ and $M = 0.2$.

518 In addition, we will highlight the advantage of high-order method in performing local p-refinement near the wall. Local refinement of the polynomial order comes from the flexibility of high-order framework, where the mesh remains unchanged but the order of polynomial inside the element can be improved. This keeps good accuracy with a much reduced degree of freedom, thus reducing the overall computational cost. 520 Although it is not the main focus of the present work, we also investigated the efficacy of local p-refinement near the wall. The p-refinement is implemented based on the mortar method [93], where a mortar element is 522

Figure 14: Comparison of variables for flow past a cylinder at $Re = 40$ and $M = 0.2$. The local p-refinement is considered near the wall. The white curve represents the solid boundary. h and P are locally uniform grid size and the polynomial order, respectively. $P1P3$ refers to the local p-refinement case with global order 1 and local order 3 near the wall.

524 introduced to the element interface. The common and interaction fluxes are computed on the mortar element
and are projected back to each neighboring face. We tested this approach based on the first mesh, where
526 the global order $P = 1$ is used for elements in the far field. Local p-refinement near the wall is performed
to improve the polynomial order locally to $P = 3$. The distribution of polynomial order across each element
528 is shown in Fig. 14a. To implement local p-refinement for the present test case, we firstly measure the
distance between each cell center and the surface of the obstacle. When this distance is smaller than $0.25D$,
530 the polynomial order of that element is increased to $P = 3$. A buffer layer with $P = 2$ is also included
between $P = 1$ and $P = 3$ cells. From the results in Fig. 14b, it is clear that with local p-refinement, we can
532 produce very close results compared with globally high-order computation. The total number of degrees of
freedom (total number of solution points) is 148296 for the test case considering p-refinement. This is nearly
534 one quarter of the degree of freedom 532576 required for the test case with uniform $P = 3$. This is also a
significant reduction compared to the 800×320 mesh based on finite difference method [90] with 256000
536 degrees of freedom. This test case shows the advantage of combining high-order methods with IBM. The
p-adaptation framework [94, 95] with proper adaptation strategy can be further considered to increase the
538 resolution on any flow region of interest.

Furthermore, since the proposed method is applied to the compressible Navier-Stokes equations, ad-
540 ditional test cases are added to show the accurate description of compressibility effects. We choose the
benchmark case from Canuto and Taira [96], where the two-dimensional compressible viscous flow around a
542 circular cylinder (based on the body-fitted grid) was studied. We simulate both steady and unsteady flows
from Mach number $M = 0.1$ to $M = 0.5$. The comparison is shown in Appendix D, where good agreement is
544 reported, and the trend of aerodynamic forces with respect to compressibility effects is accurately captured.

5.3. Flow past a NACA0012 airfoil

546 The flow over an airfoil is tested to evaluate the present method for a configuration with higher Reynolds
number and a non-zero angle of attack. The benchmark of NACA0012 airfoil at Mach number 0.5 (weakly
548 compressible flow) and Reynolds number 5000 is chosen, with an angle of attack 2 degree. The size of
rectangular computational domain is $x \in [-30c, 50c]$ and $y \in [-30c, 30c]$, where c is the chord length of the

550 airfoil. In the square region $x \in [-c, c]$ and $y \in [-c, c]$, uniform and square grid with mesh size $0.004c$ is
 used. The number of mesh elements are 897×697 . The characteristic boundary conditions are imposed to
 552 all the far field boundaries. The reference data is obtained from a body-fitted simulation of the same solver.

Figure 15: Influence of penalization parameter η for flow past a NACA0012 airfoil at $Re = 5000$ and $M = 0.5$, illustrated by C_p distribution. h and P are locally uniform grid size and the polynomial order, respectively.

The influence of penalization parameter is studied first, which is shown in Fig. 15. Here for all the cases,
 554 the polynomial order is set to $P = 2$ with a constant time step 1×10^{-4} . As the penalization parameter
 decreases, the results become more accurate. This is consistent with the error estimate that the penalization
 556 parameter should be small enough to ensure good accuracy. In addition, the smoothness of the solution
 becomes worse as penalization parameter decreases. It can be seen that when the penalization parameter is
 558 smaller than $\Delta t = 1 \times 10^{-4}$, the solution cannot be further improved, and becomes slightly more oscillatory,
 as shown in the test case with $\eta = 1 \times 10^{-5}$. This validates the argument that the error saturates around
 560 $\eta \approx \Delta t$ [84] [62].

To compare the solution with refined resolution, two more test cases are simulated. For the same mesh,
 562 the polynomial order is increased to $P = 4$, with time step and penalization parameter set to 2×10^{-5} . In
 addition, a locally refined mesh with size $0.001c$ is also generated, with 1341×365 elements. The simulation
 564 based on this mesh with $P = 2$, $\Delta t = 1 \times 10^{-5}$ and $\eta = 1 \times 10^{-5}$ is also added. As shown in the Fig. 16,
 all simulations give very good prediction on C_p . The prediction of surface skin friction coefficient is more
 566 difficult, since it involves the reconstruction of gradient. Effective ways for such reconstruction still remain

Figure 16: Comparison of pressure and friction coefficients with different h and p resolutions, for flow past a NACA0012 airfoil at $Re = 5000$ and $M = 0.5$. h and P are locally uniform grid size and the polynomial order, respectively.

an open question, where different strategies have been proposed [77, 70] and are worth investigating in future works. From Fig. 16, we can also see that as the resolution near the wall increases, C_f is better predicted. With the help of high-order methods, this increase in resolution can be achieved by either increasing the polynomial order or reducing the mesh size near the wall. Note that for low-order schemes, we need a resolution about mesh size $5 \times 10^{-4}c$ to have a comparable prediction of the friction distribution [79], as opposed to $h = 0.001c$ and $P = 2$ for high-order methods.

5.4. Flow past a sphere

In order to test the proposed method in simulating three-dimensional flows, the flow over a sphere at Reynolds number 100 and Mach number 0.2 is chosen. To reduce the overall computational cost, we generate the mesh for a quarter of the whole domain. The size of domain is $x \in [-30D, 30D]$, $y \in [0, 30D]$ and $z \in [0, 30D]$, where D is the diameter of the sphere. The symmetric plane is considered as boundary conditions for the $y = 0$ and $z = 0$ plane, while characteristic boundary conditions are imposed to all the other boundaries. To ensure sufficient resolution near the wall, uniform grid with size $0.03D$ is used in region $x \in [-0.6D, 0.6D]$, $y \in [0, 0.6D]$ and $z \in [0, 0.6D]$. This results in a total element number of $129 \times 55 \times 55$. The polynomial order is set to 2. The time step and penalization parameter are set to 5×10^{-5} .

The surface quantities from the symmetrical plane $z = 0$ are used for comparison. The resulting pressure coefficient distribution is compared with other studies from [97] and [38], which are shown in Fig. 17. From the comparison of pressure coefficient, all results nearly collapse, thus indicating the good accuracy of the present method. The comparison of wall azimuthal vorticity is shown and compared with the IBM results from Choi et al. [80]. A good agreement is also observed, except slight oscillation around the separation position. As shown in previous study, this can be reduced by further refining the resolution near the wall. The drag coefficient is about 1.06, which is only about 2% error compared with existing results (1.08 from [98] and 1.09 from [99]). This simulation lays the foundation for more complex test cases and interesting future works, e.g., unsteady compressible flow over a sphere in transonic and hypersonic flow conditions [100].

Figure 17: Comparison of variables for flow past a sphere at $Re = 100$ and $M = 0.2$. h and P are locally uniform grid size and the polynomial order, respectively. Reference data are taken from Dandy and Dwyer (1990) [97], Fadlun (2000) [38] and Choi (2007) [80].

5.5. Flow past a pitching and plunging airfoil

In this subsection, a moving airfoil with combined plunging and pitching motion is simulated with the proposed method. This configuration has been extensively considered in flapping wings [101] and FSI analysis [102]. The present case is taken from Case 2 of the 5th International Workshop on High-Order CFD Methods [103].

Figure 18: Evolution of motion evolution with time. b and θ are plunging displacement and pitching angle, respectively.

The Mach number is 0.2 and the Reynolds number is 1000. The size of rectangular computational domain is $x \in [-30c, 60c]$ and $y \in [-30c, 30c]$, where c is the chord length of the airfoil. In the rectangular region $x \in [-0.8c, 0.8c]$ and $y \in [-0.3c, 1.3c]$, uniform and square grid with size $0.005c$ is used. This results in a total number of 652×466 elements. The characteristic boundary conditions are imposed to the far field. The rotation axis is placed at $1/3$ chord length of airfoil centerline. The simulation is performed with polynomial orders from 1 to 3, with time step set to 6.0×10^{-5} , 4.0×10^{-5} and 2.5×10^{-5} , respectively. As usual, the penalization parameter is the same as the time step for all simulations. The plunging and pitching motions

604 are defined by the following equation:

$$\begin{cases} b(t) = t^3(-8t^3 + 51t^2 - 111t + 84)/16 \\ \theta(t) = (80\pi/180)t^2(t^2 - 4t + 4) \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

The displacement versus time is shown in Fig. 18. The airfoil keeps moving upward, with an impulse
 606 type pitching motion. The comparison of force coefficient in x and y directions is shown in Fig. 19. A good
 agreement with the reference data produced from body-fitted simulation [103] is observed, where all IBM
 608 simulations are quite close thus is not distinguishable from the figure.

Figure 19: Force comparison of combined plunging and pitching motion. h and P are locally uniform grid size and the polynomial order, respectively.

In order to see how the solution converges as we increase the polynomial order, a zoom-in view of force
 610 evolution is shown in Fig. 20. It can be seen that, as the polynomial order increases, the result will approach
 $P = 3$ simulation. The smoothness of solution is also improved as we increase the polynomial order. This
 612 is in consistent with the high-order framework where the higher polynomial order leads to better resolution
 and better accuracy. The flow fields based on $P = 2$ simulation is visualized in Fig. 21. From this figure,
 614 the vortex shedding pattern for such energy extraction process can be accurately described.

6. Conclusions

616 An immersed boundary method based on volume penalization for high-order flux reconstruction method
 is proposed. It comes from the aspiration to use high-order DG type methods to efficiently handle the
 618 complex geometries on Cartesian grid and to alleviate the sometimes difficult meshing procedure. FR
 approach is selected due to its capability of recovering existing high-order schemes. The volume penalization
 620 method, which is proven to show convergence under low penalization parameter limit, is introduced as the
 IBM approach. Our implementation is general and does not assume knowing the analytical shape of the
 622 geometry, which enables generalisation to complex three-dimensional simulations. In order to overcome the
 numerical stability issue coming from stiff IBM source term, the splitting scheme with explicit and implicit

Figure 20: Detailed comparison of force across different polynomial orders. h and P are locally uniform grid size and the polynomial order, respectively.

Figure 21: Flow snapshots at four time instants for combined pitching and plunging motion of the airfoil. The locally uniform grid size is $h = 0.005$ and the polynomial order is $P = 2$.

624 forcing methods are proposed, where the latter is a novel approach to handle the IBM source term. Efficient
and accurate methods for reconstructing flow quantities near the wall are used to get the surface pressure and
626 friction distribution. Through simulating the one-dimensional advection-diffusion equation, the convergence
behavior is investigated. It highlights the importance of increasing resolution near the wall and the use of
628 small penalization parameter to impose the boundary condition properly. The accuracy of the proposed
method has been validated through different real flow cases including flow past static cylinder, airfoil and
630 sphere, as well as unsteady flow past a moving airfoil. Good agreement with body-fitted simulation and
existing literature is shown, indicating the validity of the proposed method. In addition, the high accuracy
632 of the flux reconstruction method provided when using high-order polynomials is evident in the results, and
particularly when computing surface functionals (e.g. lift, drag), in both static and moving geometries.
634 Further work will extend and enhance the present method to compute complex three-dimensional turbulent
flows in the FSI context.

636 Conflict of Interest

The work presented in this paper does not have any conflict of interest with other organizations.

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Appendix A. Analytical mask function for different geometries

642 Although the present work has developed a method to calculate mask function for arbitrary geometries,
analytical mask functions for the geometries involved in the present study are also given for completeness.
644 For a cylinder, a sphere, and a NACA0012 airfoil with unit length, whose center point is located at $(0, 0, 0)$,
the mask function is given as follows:

For cylinder:

$$\chi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x^2 + y^2 \leq 0.5^2 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \quad (\text{A.1})$$

For sphere:

$$\chi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x^2 + y^2 + z^2 \leq 0.5^2 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \quad (\text{A.2})$$

For NACA0012 airfoil:

$$\chi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } y^2 - (a_1(a_2\sqrt{(x+0.5)} + a_3(x+0.5) + a_4(x+0.5)^2 + a_5(x+0.5)^3 + a_6(x+0.5)^4))^2 \leq 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \quad (\text{A.3})$$

646 the coefficients for NACA0012 airfoils are $a_1 = 0.594689181$, $a_2 = 0.298222773$, $a_3 = -0.127125232$, $a_4 =$
 -0.357907906 , $a_5 = 0.291984971$, and $a_6 = -0.105174606$.

648 **Appendix B. Smoothing the mask function**

As mentioned in [60, 62], smoothing the mask function enables to avoid spurious oscillations of the hydrodynamic forces on moving obstacles, and also helps for de-aliasing of the penalization term. In order to test how smoothing mask function helps with the present solver, we make a test on simulating the NACA0012 airfoil for the same case considered in Sec. 5.3. Following [60], we use a Gaussian function to smooth the sharp mask function χ_{sharp} :

$$\chi_{smooth} = [1 - \exp(-(x_{dist}/\delta)^2)] \cdot \chi_{sharp}, \tag{B.1}$$

654 where x_{dist} refers to the distance of solution point to the surface, δ is the width of the smoothing function. As an example, the one-dimensional smooth mask function with different width parameters is shown in Fig. B.22. As the solution point is approaching the surface, less penalization is imposed.

Figure B.22: Smooth mask function with different width.

We select the $h = 0.004, P = 2$ test case for NACA0012 airfoil, with penalization parameter 1×10^{-5} . Two width parameters, $h/3$ and $h/8$ are considered. The results are shown in Fig. B.23. It is observed that with the smooth mask function, the pressure distribution becomes less oscillatory, while some error will also be introduced near the leading edge of the skin friction coefficient. This is related to the smaller source term near the wall, where the accuracy may be reduced but the smoothness of the solution can be improved. We can also see that as a larger width parameter is selected, the accuracy of the result becomes worse. This comparison shows that for the present problem, smoothing the mask function will help to reduce oscillations near the wall, but will not lead to any gain in accuracy. Therefore we choose to use a sharp mask function for all simulations in this paper. However, different smoothing strategies are still worth testing to see if an optimal smoothing approach exists, which improves both the accuracy and smoothness of force prediction.

Appendix C. Comparison of data reconstruction methods

668 As discussed in Sec. 4.4, for the present method, it is straightforward to employ the high-order polynomial interpolation to get the quantities of interest for surface marker points. However, basic analysis on the interpolation stencil shows that such operation will involve the solution points immersed solid that have nonphysical values and gradients. A comparison of data reconstruction methods is made here to show the difference between the polynomial interpolation and the IDW-IP method used in the present study. We take

Figure B.23: Comparison of using smooth mask function for flow past a NACA0012 airfoil at $Re = 5000$, $M = 0.5$ and angle of attack 2 degree.

the third result from Sec. 5.2, where flow past a cylinder at Reynolds number 40 is simulated. The third
674 mesh with locally uniform grid size $0.01D$ is selected and the polynomial order is set to 2. We take the
676 final flow field, and reconstruct the surface quantities based on both methods. The comparison of pressure
678 coefficient and wall spanwise vorticity is shown in Fig. C.24. It is clearly seen that the pressure coefficient
680 from high-order polynomial interpolation shows very large oscillation, while results from IDW-IP are smooth
and agree well with body-fitted simulation. The under-prediction of wall spanwise vorticity from high-order
polynomial interpolation is evident in Fig. C.24b, where the result is not only oscillatory but also does not
fit the body-fitted simulation. This highlights the weakness of using high-order polynomial to interpolate
flow quantities on the surface.

Figure C.24: Comparison of data reconstruction method for flow past a cylinder at $Re = 40$ and $M = 0.2$.

682 Appendix D. Test case of compressibility effect

Since the present method is applied to the compressible Navier-Stokes equations, it is important to chal-
684 lenge the method to capture compressibility effects. This section focuses on the capability of the present

method in capturing the compressibility effects and the unsteady flow dynamics. A two-dimensional compressible viscous flow around a circular cylinder is considered, where the reference data from body-fitted simulation is given by Canuto and Taira [96]. We select two Reynolds numbers, including $Re = 40$ and $Re = 100$, which represent typical steady and unsteady flows, respectively.

The computational grid for both test cases is the locally uniform grid in the square region $x \in [-0.6D, 0.6D]$ and $y \in [-0.6D, 0.6D]$, where D is the diameter of the cylinder and is set to 1. The size of the rectangular computational domain is $x \in [-20D, 40D]$ and $y \in [-20D, 20D]$. For $Re = 40$, the uniform mesh size h is set to $0.015D$, and the number elements is 140×132 . For $Re = 100$, the uniform mesh size h is set to $0.02D$, and the number elements is 562×116 . To simulate unsteady flows, the wake region has been refined in order capture the vortex shedding. The polynomial order is set to $P = 2$. The time step and penalization parameters are selected following the usual procedure, which are 2×10^{-5} and 4×10^{-5} for steady and unsteady cases, respectively.

(a) Mean drag coefficient

(b) Characteristic wake properties at $Re = 40$. L_a : the horizontal distance to separation bubble center. L_b : the vertical distance between separation bubble centers. L_r : the separation bubble length.

(c) Maximal lift coefficient at $Re = 100$

(d) Strouhal number at $Re = 100$

Figure D.25: Comparison of compressibility effects of flow around a circular cylinder. Empty symbols are the reference data from [96].

Comparison of different quantities of interest is shown in Figure D.25. These quantities include the mean drag coefficient, characteristic wake properties, maximal lift coefficient and the Strouhal number. The characteristic wake properties [96] include the horizontal distance to separation bubble center L_a , the vertical distance between separation bubble centers L_b , and the separation bubble length L_r . It should be noted that

the second set of quantities is used for the steady flow, while the third and the fourth sets of quantity are used for the unsteady flow. From these figures, good agreement is observed. Note that small discrepancies in drag have been reported in the literature [104, 91, 92, 105, 106, 80, 50, 96], at $Re = 40$ (in the incompressible flow), which varies from 1.48 to 1.59.

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